

and the outermost cell walls. In general, iron coatings appear as porous or dense materials filling the lumens (Photo 1). In a rare case, FeOOH precipitated into lumens with all the cell walls intact and formed an iron cast the shape of the original epidermal cell (Photo 2). The hollow interior on the left cast with a broken end indicates that precipitation begins on the cell walls. No visible coating showed on younger secondary roots and sections of roots near the tips. ■

1. Representative view of iron coating on rice root. L: lumen, I: iron coating.

2. Special case of iron coating formation. IC: iron casts of epidermal cells, E: broken end of a cast.

Performance of new rice entries at different planting dates and nitrogen rates

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The timely planting of rice is important in testing the yield level of any rice variety because it enables the plant to utilize more efficiently the environment in which it is grown. In general early planting (first week of June) of medium-duration varieties results in higher yield. In case of short-duration varieties, planting time does not greatly affect the grain yield of rice. A field experiment at the Crop Research Centre of G. B. Pant University of Agriculture & Technology, Pantnagar, during 1977 kharif tested the performance of newly developed rice varieties.

Effect of planting dates on grain yield of rice varieties grown under different levels of nitrogen. Pantnagar, India, 1977 kharif.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	1 June		16 June		1 July	
	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
Jaya	6.1	6.7	6.2	6.9	5.5	6.5
UPR103 D-6-1	5.5	6.5	5.3	5.6	4.4	4.8
UPR171-12	5.3	6.5	5.2	6.4	5.4	5.8
UPR73-23	6.0	6.7	6.0	6.3	5.5	5.9
IET2815	5.9	6.8	6.1	6.7	5.1	6.4
Ratna	5.9	6.7	6.1	6.2	6.5	5.5
Saket 4	6.1	6.7	6.4	6.3	5.3	6.0
UPR4-D-1-1	6.3	6.3	5.4	5.6	5.2	5.6
UPR82-1-7	5.6	6.3	6.1	6.2	5.7	5.9
IR36	6.2	7.0	5.6	6.4	5.3	6.0
			S.Em.±	C.D. at 5%	C.V. (%)	
Date × nitrogen × variety			0.23	0.64	7	
Nitrogen × variety			0.13	0.37		

Jaya gave maximum yield when planted on 16 June; UPR103-D-61, UPR1 71-12, UPR73-23, UPR4-D-1-1, and IR36 gave higher yields when planted on 1 June, irrespective of nitro-

gen dose. Ratna, Saket 4, IET2815, UPR82-1-7 yielded more when planted 16 June with 60 kg N/ha than when planted 1 July with 120 kg N/ha (see table). ■

Neem cake-blended urea for increased nitrogen use efficiency in transplanted rice

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When nitrogen fertilizers are added to soil, their efficiency is reduced considerably — sometimes to the extent of 50%

or less — because of leaching, denitrification, volatilization, and surface runoff. There is a need for some simple and cheap device to reduce these losses. One device found effective under the different soil conditions prevailing in Karnataka is blending ordinary urea with nonedible neem cake available locally. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) trees grow abundantly in India.

The technique consists of mixing well-powdered, country-pressed neem cake

with ordinary urea (30% by wt). Adherence of neem cake powder to urea granules is very important in the blending process. To ensure that, the powder and granules are mixed well 1 or 2 days ahead of application. The mixture is incorporated uniformly in equal doses at the time of planting and tilling.

Better adherence of neem cake to urea granules is obtained by using a coal tar (used for road surfacing) and kerosene oil mixture in 1:2 proportions while

blending, especially when deoiled neem cake is used. When that mixture is used, the neem cake-urea blend may be applied in a single dose, also saving the cost of topdressing. This is more practical in situations where effective topdressing is not easily done, as in coastal districts of North and South Canara where water management is a problem.

Neem cake obtained from a country press generally contains an average 2% nitrogen, 14% crude fat, 1.2% total calcium oxide, and 0.21% total P₂O₅. The effectiveness of neem cake results from an alkaloid content, such as "Nimbidin," which helps to regulate mineralization and minimize nitrogen losses.

Experiments on the efficacy of neem cake-blended urea in transplanted rice were conducted over four seasons at Mandya centre (see table). The soil type of the experimental site was red sandy

Grain yield and uptake of nitrogen and phosphorus in grain using neem cake-blended urea.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Nitrogen content in grain (%)	Phosphorus content in grain (%)
Neem cake-blended urea using coal tar and kerosene oil, at 80 kg N/ha, all basal	5.2	32	1.4	0.8
Neem cake-blended urea alone, in 2 splits, at 80 kg N/ha	4.7	26	1.3	0.8
Ordinary urea in splits (3) at 100 kg N/ha, recommended practice	4.2	12	1.1	0.7
Control - no nitrogen	2.6	-	0.7	0.5
F Test	**			
C.D. (0.05)	0.4			
C.V. (%)	8.9			

loam (Alfisols) with pH 6.8, less than 0.2 mmho total soluble salts/cm, 0.6% organic carbon, 19.2 kg available phosphorus/ha, and 268.3 kg potassium/ha. All recommended practices were followed. The results indicate that blending

urea with neem cake saved nitrogen fertilizer to the extent of 20% and increased yield up to 15%.

The additional cost for preparing neem cake-blended urea was about US\$5/ha for ingredients and labor. ■

Role of higher nitrogen rate, sulfur, and zinc application in bridging the yield gap of farmer's boro rice in Bangladesh

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Boro rice (transplanted Dec-Jan, harvested Apr-May) usually gives the highest yield per hectare of all the types of rice grown in Bangladesh. The crop is irrigated and farmers generally apply to it a higher intensity management, including fertilizer, than that for aus, transplanted aman, and deepwater rice.

In many cases, however, farmers do not apply adequate amounts of fertilizer to the boro crop. This ultimately reduces yields. Furthermore, in many boro rice-growing areas, soil problems are increasingly evident, particularly because of the continuous wet conditions of the soil in the irrigation projects.

At the BRRI cropping systems research site at Salna, sulfur (S) and zinc (Zn) deficiencies recently were detected. A complete factorial trial with three replications was conducted in 1979-80 in a farmer's field to determine the effect of a higher rate of N, and application of S

Effect of higher rate of N, S, and Zn application on the yield of BR3 boro rice, 1979-80 boro season, Salna village, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Fertilizer rate		Zn (%) used in ZnO suspension in water for root dipping	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Panicles (no./hill) ^a	Plant ht(cm) at harvest ^a	Straw yield ^b (t/ha)
Kg N/ha	Kg S/ha					
40	None	None	3.80 e	8.9 d	73 b	5.1 c
40	None	1.6	3.87 e	8.9 d	73 b	5.4 bc
40	11.3	None	4.35 d	9.3 cd	78 a	5.9 abc
40	11.3	1.6	4.43 cd	9.7 bcd	76 a	5.6 bc
80	None	None	4.54 bcd	10.4 bc	77 a	5.9 abc
80	None	1.6	4.85 abc	11.1 b	78 a	6.5 abc
80	11.3	None	4.92 ab	12.5 a	79 a	6.8 a
80	11.3	1.6	5.09 a	13.2a	80 a	6.9 a

^a In the column, values having a common letter do not differ significantly at the 1% level of significance. ^b In the column, values having a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level of significance.

and Zn, on the grain yield of BR3 variety. Ammonium sulfate was the source of S, and the treatment consisted of dipping seedling roots in 2% ZnO suspension in water before transplanting.

The results indicate that a rate of 80 kg N/ha gave a significantly higher grain yield than the farmer's rate of 40 kg N/ha (see table). At the farmer's N level, the Zn treatment did not significantly influence grain yield, but S application increased it. At both levels of N, application of S with or without Zn gave statistically similar grain yields.

But in all cases the Zn treatment gave some quantitative increase in grain yield. The yield gap was 1.3 t/ha, and the contributions of higher N, S, and Zn in bridging the gap were 0.70 (53%), 0.45 (34%), and 0.18 (13%) t/ha.

The number of panicles per hill, plant height, and straw yield also were influenced significantly by the treatments (see table). Results of the present experiment indicate that a higher rate of N and application of S are important for obtaining the potential yield of boro rice at this site. ■